

SUPPLEMENT 4. Information of the collections used for Phylogenies 4 and 5. Those collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. Holotypes, epitypes and neotypes are indicated by HT, ET and NT, respectively. For Phylogeny 4, only those collections with sequence data complete in the four loci are included. For Phylogeny 5, the ITS sequences of all collections are included.

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1α</i>	<i>β-tub</i>	
Ingroup								
<i>Candolleomyces</i>	<i>Cd. aberdarensis</i>	GLMF116094 (HT)	Germany	MH880928	-	-	-	Melzer <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Cd. albipes</i>	DED8340	Sao Tome and Principe	KX017209	-	-	-	Desjardin & Perry (2016)
	<i>Cd. albosquamosus</i>	TBGT18600 (HT)	India	OQ676550	-	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2023a)
	<i>Cd. albosquamosus</i>	TBGT18895	India	OQ676549	-	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2023a)
	<i>Cd. albovagabundus</i>	HKAS129660 (HT)	China	OR711041	OR711057	OR727285	-	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. albovagabundus</i>	L23198	China	OR711042	OR711058	OR727286	-	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. amygdaliformis</i>	LAH37634 (HT)	Pakistan	PP375293	PP375296	-	-	Ahmad <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. amygdaliformis</i>	LAH37635	Pakistan	PP375294	PP375297	-	-	Ahmad <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. asiaticus</i>	LAH36809 (HT)	Pakistan	NR182405	OQ802842	-	-	Asif <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Cd. badhyzensis</i>	TAA79478 (HT)	Turkmenistan	KC992883	KC992883	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Cd. badiophyllus</i>	NL2347	Unknown	FN430699	FM876268	FM897252	FN396261	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cd. bivelatus</i>	MCVE29117	Italy	MF325962	-	-	-	Voto <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	<i>Cd. bivelatus</i>	110114MFBPZH0777	Unknown	MW554021	-	-	-	Direct submission by Zhou
	<i>Cd. brevisporus</i>	HMAS258919 (HT)	China	OR822167	OR822149	OR819986	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. brevisporus</i>	HMAS258920	China	OR822168	OR822150	OR819987	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. brunneovagabundus</i>	HKAS129659 (HT)	China	OR711031	OR711047	OR791600	-	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. brunneovagabundus</i>	L23209	China	OR711045	OR711061	OR727289	OR727292	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. brunneopileatus</i>	TBGT(M)18698 (HT)	India	OQ878348	OR244401	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2023b)
	<i>Cd. brunneopileatus</i>	TBGT(M)18553	India	OQ878483	OR244398	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2023b)
	<i>Cd. cacao</i>	DED8339 (HT)	Sao Tome and Principe	KX017210	-	-	-	Desjardin & Perry (2016)
	<i>Cd. cacao</i>	FP1R4	USA	KU847452	-	-	-	Bayman <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Cd. cacao</i>	MP2R2	USA	KU847436	-	-	-	Bayman <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Cd. campanulatus</i>	LAH35719 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ308881	OQ802837	-	-	Izhar <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. campanulatus</i>	LAH37657	Pakistan	OQ308882	OQ802838	-	-	Izhar <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i>	LAS73030 (NT)	Sweden	KM030175	KM030175	-	-	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HKAS145960	China	PV155138	PV147315	PV156663	PV156700	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HKAS145961	China	PV155149	PV147326	PV156673	PV156711	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM0640	China	PV155142	PV147319	PV156666	PV156704	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM0755	China	PV155164	PV147341	-	PV156725	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM0799	China	PV155161	PV147338	PV156685	-	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM0800	China	PV155166	PV147343	PV156689	PV156727	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM0822	China	PV155167	PV147344	PV156690	PV156728	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM0904	China	PV155135	PV147312	PV156660	PV156697	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM1357	China	PV155136	PV147313	PV156661	PV156698	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM1369	China	PV155137	PV147314	PV156662	PV156699	This study

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SUPPLEMENT 4. (continued)

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1a</i>	<i>β-tub</i>	
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM1399	China	PV155163	PV147340	PV156687	PV156724	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM1548	China	PV155160	PV147337	PV156684	PV156722	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM1941	China	PV155145	PV147322	PV156669	PV156707	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2162	China	PV155146	PV147323	PV156670	PV156708	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2172	China	PV155147	PV147324	PV156671	PV156709	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2174	China	PV155150	PV147327	PV156674	PV156712	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2175	China	PV155151	PV147328	PV156675	PV156713	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2176	China	PV155152	PV147329	PV156676	PV156714	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2184	China	PV155153	PV147330	PV156677	PV156715	This study
	<i>Cd. candolleanus</i> complex	HTBM2185	China	PV155154	PV147331	PV156678	PV156716	This study
	<i>Cd. cladii-marisci</i>	CLUF302 (HT)	Italy	MK080112	-	-	-	Sicoli <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	<i>Cd. crenatus</i>	LAH38257 (HT)	Pakistan	PQ329548	PQ329553	PQ369432	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2025)
	<i>Cd. crenatus</i>	LAH38258	Pakistan	PQ329547	PQ329554	PQ369433	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2025)
	<i>Cd. duboissoniae</i>	BRIP76349a (HT)	Australia	PQ431205	PQ431198	-	-	Tan & Shivas (2024)
	<i>Cd. efflorescens</i>	Pegler2133	Sri Lanka	KC992941	-	-	-	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. efflorescens</i> complex	HTBM0525	China	PV155132	PV147309	PV156657	PV156695	This study
	<i>Cd. efflorescens</i> complex	HTBM0657	China	PV155148	PV147325	PV156672	PV156710	This study
	<i>Cd. euryspor</i>	GLMF126263 (HT)	Germany	MT651560	MT651560	-	-	Büttner <i>et al.</i> (2020)
	<i>Cd. granulosis</i>	LAH38105 (HT)	Pakistan	PP058337	PP058343	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
	<i>Cd. granulosis</i>	LAH38106	Pakistan	PP058338	PP058344	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
	<i>Cd. gyirongicus</i>	HMAS287612 (HT)	China	PP734613	PP734624	PP729326	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. gyirongicus</i>	HMAS287613	China	PP734614	PP734625	PP729327	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. halophila</i>	MICH AH-14321	Spain	MG825900	-	-	-	Broussal <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Cd. incanus</i>	BJTCZ777 (HT)	China	ON042759	ON042766	ON098508	ON098513	Zhou <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Cd. incanus</i>	BJTCS173	China	ON042760	ON042767	ON098509	ON098514	Zhou <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Cd. iqbalii</i>	LAH35327 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ968353	OQ968366	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. iqbalii</i>	LAH35328	Pakistan	OQ968354	OQ968365	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. iqbalii</i>	LAH37971	Pakistan	OR607882	-	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. iqbalii</i> complex	HTBM1416	China	PV155141	PV147318	-	PV156703	This study
	<i>Cd. kotadduensis</i>	LAH37636 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ968359	OQ968362	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. kotadduensis</i>	LAH37637	Pakistan	OQ968360	OQ968361	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. leucotephrus</i>	LO13801	Sweden	KC992885	KC992885	KJ732775	KJ664865	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. lignicola</i>	HMAS258921 (HT)	China	OR822169	OR822151	OR819988	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. lignicola</i>	HMAS258922	China	OR822170	OR822152	OR819989	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. luridus</i>	HMAS258913 (HT)	China	OR822161	OR822143	OR819980	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. luridus</i>	HMAS258915	China	OR822163	OR822145	OR819982	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. luteopallidus</i>	Sharp20863 (HT)	USA	KC992884	KC992884	-	-	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. luteopallidus</i>	HMJAU5148	China	MG734736	MW301084	MW314073	MW314056	Yan & Bau (2018)
	<i>Cd. luteopallidus</i> complex	HTBM1391	China	PV155162	PV147339	PV156686	PV156723	This study
	<i>Cd. luteopallidus</i> complex	HTBM1436	China	PV155143	PV147320	PV156667	PV156705	This study
	<i>Cd. niveofloccosus</i>	TBGT(M)18412 (HT)	India	OQ878345	OR244387	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2023b)
	<i>Cd. niveofloccosus</i>	TBGT(M)18513	India	OQ878251	OR244394	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2023b)

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SUPPLEMENT 4. (continued)

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1a</i>	<i>β-tub</i>	
	<i>Cd. niveosquamosus</i>	TBGT(M)18773 (HT)	India	PP741631	PP741635	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2024)
	<i>Cd. niveosquamosus</i>	TBGT(M)19023	India	PP741632	PP741634	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2024)
	<i>Cd. pabbiensis</i>	LAH35326 (HT)	Pakistan	PP058339	PP058345	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
	<i>Cd. pabbiensis</i>	LAH38107	Pakistan	PP058340	PP058346	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
	<i>Cd. pakistanicus</i>	LAH37829 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ968356	OQ968363	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. pakistanicus</i>	LAH37830	Pakistan	OQ968355	OQ968364	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. parvipileus</i>	LAH37840 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ968357	OR506278	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. parvipileus</i>	LAH37841	Pakistan	OQ968358	-	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024b)
	<i>Cd. pseudocandolleanus</i>	HMJAU35981	Unknown	KY120973	-	-	-	Direct submission by Bau & Yan
	<i>Cd. rogueianus</i>	MICH12031 (HT)	USA	MW412407	-	-	-	Direct submission by Gordon
	<i>Cd. rubrobrunneus</i>	TBGT(M)19475 (HT)	India	PP741633	PP741636	-	-	Nayana & Pradeep (2024)
	<i>Cd. rubrobrunneus</i> complex	HTBM0773	China	PV155165	PV147342	PV156688	PV156726	This study
	<i>Cd. rubrobrunneus</i> complex	HTBM0877	China	PV155134	PV147311	PV156659	PV156696	This study
	<i>Cd. rubrobrunneus</i> complex	HTBM1407	China	PV155139	PV147316	PV156664	PV156701	This study
	<i>Cd. rubrobrunneus</i> complex	HTBM1409	China	PV155140	PV147317	PV156665	PV156702	This study
	<i>Cd. rubrobrunneus</i> complex	HTBM1449	China	PV155144	PV147321	PV156668	PV156706	This study
	<i>Cd. ruhunensis</i>	HKAS123158 (HT)	Sri Lanka	ON685315	-	-	-	Ediriweera <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. secotioides</i>	UES2918 (HT)	Mexico	KR003281	KR003282	KR003283	-	Moreno <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. shennongdingicus</i>	HMAS258918 (HT)	China	OR822166	OR822148	OR819985	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. shennongdingicus</i>	HMAS258917	China	OR822165	OR822147	OR819984	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. shennongjianus</i>	HMAS258909 (HT)	China	OR822157	OR822139	OR819976	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. shennongjianus</i>	HMAS258907	China	OR822155	OR822137	OR819974	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. sichuanicus</i>	HMAS287616 (HT)	China	PP734617	PP734628	PP729330	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. sichuanicus</i>	HMAS287617	China	PP734618	PP734629	PP729331	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. sindhudeltae</i>	LAH37632 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ247908	OQ247912	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. singeri</i>	HMJAU37867	China	MG734718	MW301088	MW314077	MW314059	Yan & Bau (2018)
	<i>Cd. singeri</i>	HMJAU37877	China	MW301073	MW301091	MW314080	MW314062	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. singeri</i>	HMAS258923	China	OR822171	OR822153	OR819990	-	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Cd. singeri</i> complex	HTBM2193	China	PV155155	PV147332	PV156679	PV156717	This study
	<i>Cd. singeri</i> complex	HTBM2194	China	PV155156	PV147333	PV156680	PV156718	This study
	<i>Cd. singeri</i> complex	HTBM2195	China	PV155157	PV147334	PV156681	PV156719	This study
	<i>Cd. singeri</i> complex	HTBM2196	China	PV155158	PV147335	PV156682	PV156720	This study
	<i>Cd. singeri</i> complex	HTBM2197	China	PV155159	PV147336	PV156683	PV156721	This study
	<i>Cd. subcacao</i>	HMJAU37807 (HT)	China	MW301064	MW301092	MW314081	MW314063	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subcacao</i>	HFJAU1014	China	MW559218	-	-	-	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subcacao</i>	HFJAU1274	China	MW559219	-	-	-	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subcacao</i>	HFJAU1488	China	MW559220	-	-	-	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subminutisporus</i>	HMJAU37801 (HT)	China	MW301066	MW301094	MW314083	MW314065	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subminutisporus</i>	HMJAU37916	China	MW301067	MW301095	MW314084	MW314066	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subsingeri</i>	HMJAU37811 (HT)	China	MG734715	MW301097	MW314085	MW314067	Yan & Bau (2018), Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. subsingeri</i>	HMJAU37913	China	MG734725	MW301098	MW314086	MW314068	Yan & Bau (2018), Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. sulcatotuberculosis</i>	LO5512	Germany	KJ138422	KJ138422	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson

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SUPPLEMENT 4. (continued)

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1α</i>	<i>β-tub</i>	
	<i>Cd. sulcatotuberculosis</i>	HFJAU1515	China	MW375696	-	MW382965	MW382967	Bau & Yan (2021)
	<i>Cd. sulcatotuberculosis</i>	Chiarello07102013	Italy	KJ138423	-	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson
	<i>Cd. sultanii</i>	LAH35714 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ308835	OQ801565	-	-	Izhar <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. sultanii</i>	LAH37658	Pakistan	OQ308836	OQ801566	-	-	Izhar <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. trinitatensis</i>	TL9035	Ecuador	KC992882	KC992882	-	KJ664863	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. tuberculatus</i>	ADK4162	Togo	KC992886	KC992886	-	-	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. tuberculatus</i>	ADK3564	Benin	KC992934	-	-	-	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cd. typhae</i>	LO2104	Sweden	DQ389721	DQ389721	KJ732776	KJ664866	Larsson & Örstadius (2008)
	<i>Cd. typhae</i> complex	HTBM1875	China	PV155133	PV147310	PV156658	-	This study
	<i>Cd. umbonatus</i>	LAH38108 (HT)	Pakistan	PP058341	PP058347	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
	<i>Cd. umbonatus</i>	LAH38109	Pakistan	PP058342	PP058348	-	-	Haqnawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024a)
	<i>Cd. undulatus</i>	LAH38255 (HT)	Pakistan	PQ329546	PQ329551	PQ369428	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2025)
	<i>Cd. undulatus</i>	LAH38256	Pakistan	PQ329545	PQ329552	PQ369429	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2025)
	<i>Cd. virgatus</i>	LAH38259 (HT)	Pakistan	PQ329543	PQ329549	PQ369430	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2025)
	<i>Cd. virgatus</i>	LAH38260	Pakistan	PQ329544	PQ329550	PQ369431	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2025)
	" <i>Cd. punjabensis</i> "	W10	Pakistan	PP386162	-	-	-	Direct submission by Akram & Saba
	" <i>Cd. punjabensis</i> "	W17	Pakistan	PP386163	-	-	-	Direct submission by Akram & Saba
Outgroup								
<i>Hausknechtia</i>	<i>H. floriformis</i>	WU22833 (HT)	Vanuatu	JX968254	JX968371	JX968458	-	Tóth <i>et al.</i> (2013)
	<i>H. leucosticta</i>	HFJAU1486 (ET)	China	OL435561	OL435565	OL439896	ON677539	Nie <i>et al.</i> (2022)